

Urban and peri-urban agriculture (UPA): from benefits to planning.

Results from EFUA H2020 project¹

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Many cities have recently understood the great potential of urban and peri-urban agriculture (UPA). UPA provides several benefits that concern different dimensions of the urban environment and, if appropriately guided and supported, can contribute considerably to the achievement of the main targets of urban agendas. However, UPA is not yet totally and formally recognised and integrated into land use policies and planning tools. Understanding how to take advantage of benefits, encourage and support decision makers to promote and sustain UPA, in order to overcome some city-related issues, is still a crucial activity for urban planning.

In this paper the authors illustrate the main results of the European Forum on Urban Agriculture (EFUA), an ongoing H2020 research project (2020-2024) which aims to unlock UPA potential by improving knowledge, networking, deployment and policies. The integration of UPA into the EU, national, regional and local policies is another specific goal of this research project. This project includes 11 partners from all over Europe and involves not only academia but also practitioners, government, farmers, and civil society. The involvement of these stakeholders enabled the establishment of a European UPA forum.

Nowadays UPA can take various forms. It includes professional and non-professional agricultural practices, both in intra-urban areas and in peri-urban spaces. UPA ranges from professional farmers who cultivate in order to satisfy local demand and citizens that cultivate their own gardens with social or recreational purposes. Using proximity to the city, UPA can provide several goods and services for urban consumers and areas. EFUA has recently identified six types of UPA: Urban Farms, Community Parks, DIY Gardens/Farms, Zero Acreage Farms, Social Farms and Community Gardensⁱ. Considering these forms, EFUA has also classified five benefits categories: socio-cultural, environmental and climate, food, health and well-being and economicⁱⁱ. EFUA has also showed that these benefits are linked with urban policy targets including the main sustainable development goals and the themes of the European Urban Agenda. This means that UPA can contribute to overcome some urban issues, especially concerning social exclusion and disparities, food poverty and insecurity, as well as the quality of urban ecosystems. Furthermore, UPA may also play a crucial role in the debates on the new "Nature restoration law" and on possible "Common food policy" for the European Union.

Supporting urban policies and spatial planning to reach these targets by using the benefits of UPA is a crucial point of this research. For these reasons, EFUA has studied the main characteristics of UPA initiatives and the barriers that limit the development of UPA, and has collected a comprehensive set of urban planning approaches supporting UPA developmentⁱⁱⁱ. EFUA analysed 44 case studies at city level, both within and outside Europe, as well as cities from LDCs, in order to transfer successful experiences and tools to the EU and local levels. EFUA highlighted that UPA has recently been addressed by many policies, at different levels and throughout the world. These policies are related to different thematic domains such as urban-rural partnerships, urban green development and management, climate adaptation and/or mitigation, local community development, urban renewal, and food strategies. These policies concerned various types of policy instruments (such as strategy, programme, project, land-use zoning, regulation, etc.) and can be grouped into two systems: the first focuses on UPA by a dedicated strategy while in the second UPA is part of a more comprehensive policy which addresses many issues or concerns a specific theme. Based on the case study analysis, EFUA also classified a scheme of the main UPA-related planning and management tools that includes inventories, plans, regulations, incentives, and assessment instruments.

Based on the literature review, the stakeholders involvement, and the analysis of case studies at city level, the research also identified challenges and needs when planning for and with UPA. EFUA showed that the main obstacles to maintain and develop UPA concern land accessibility, availability and ownership, as well as the current limitations caused by local regulations and/or zoning codes. Providing land for UPA, integrating UPA into urban policies and creating specific strategies or plans for UPA are the main challenges that urban public polices should address in order to support UPA, according to the EFUA results.

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To support city authorities in the development and integration of UPA into public policies, EFUA proposed 9 recommendations (see poster). Establishing a UPA committee and promoting a participatory approach can help to assist policy makers and to define tailored measures for differentiated UPA initiatives. The results of the EFUA project showed that keeping or making spaces for UPA, identifying existing and potential land, as well as improving its accessibility, are other crucial points for UPA. Developing tools such as site-specific strategies, land use and management regulations, financial, training and incentive instruments, evaluating and monitoring the development and impacts of UPA initiatives, are all measures that should be adopted at the city level. Finally, creating facilities and infrastructures, as well as promoting different forms and products of UPA initiatives are actions that can further maximise UPA benefits.

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9 Keys to successful UPA-related public policies and planning tools

This poster shows some results of the European Forum on Urban Agriculture (EFUA), an ongoing H2020 research project (2020-2024) which aims to unlock UPA potential by improving knowledge, networking, deployment and policies. UPA provides several benefits that concern different dimensions of the urban environment and, if appropriately guided and supported, can contribute considerably to the achievement of the main targets of urban agendas. However, UPA is not yet totally and formally recognised and integrated into land use policies and planning tools. To maximise UPA benefits and support city authorities in the development and integration of UPA into public policies, EFUA proposed these following 9 recommendations:

UPA should be implemented on the basis of a participatory planning process, engaging different stakeholders and defining a UPA committee or public department/agency involves the identification of specific governmental responsibility concerning UPA at city level. The committee should include the private sector, non-governmental organisations, NGOs, associations and different public departments related to UPA issues. The committee should aim to support policy makers and evaluate the progress and outcomes of UPA policies over time. Moreover, the committee should observe the constant process of diversification of UPA and promote tools to adapt public policies to new developments and practices.

Cities and public bodies should ensure the availability and access for UPA to urban and peri-urban public land for agricultural use, in order to significantly contribute to the conservation and enhancement of urban green spaces and agricultural land. This can be achieved by acquiring private properties, through the definition of long-term concessions, as well as developing various forms of land acquisition such as taxpayer bonds, the integration of UPA into public parks, etc. Urban land for agricultural use should also be protected through specific zoning limitations.

Creating inventories of existing plots and urban farms, as well as available (public and private) land with potential use for implementing professional UPA and urban gardening - including underutilised, abandoned, marginal and degraded lands, brownfield sites and rooftops - is crucial to support UPA. This step should include the collection of baseline data on agricultural activities, the development of a land database and a land bank, as well as the identification and analysis of the main stakeholders. This step also includes the identification of potential barriers for UPA, including urban farming and how existing urban policies limit the development of UPA.

UPA should be planned and implemented on the basis of a participatory planning process involving a wide range of community actors, and in accordance with regulations on farmland protection at the supra-local scale. UPA plans should be coordinated and integrated into land use planning, with other sectoral policies and more comprehensive strategies and plans at city level. Plans should identify different UA types (professional and not professional), define strategies for UPA development, recognizing UPA as a specific (existing or new) zone in the land use designation system.

Regulations should support land-use zoning and urban policies, as well as define what is permitted and what is not. Regulations can include guidelines and requirements to implement urban gardens, allocation mechanisms for urban gardens, rules for agricultural temporary use of public vacant or underused plots, by-laws on animal and livestock management, sale activities (direct sales on farms, location of farmer markets, including stocking and accessibility), and restrictions on the use of resources such as water and energy (irrigation systems, water abstraction, etc.).

The lack of funds and financial instruments are the main factors usually leading to the failure of UPA initiatives. Financial resources include not only subsidies or block grant funds for maintaining and developing existing UPA initiatives, but also fees, tax rebates and reductions, abatements and exemptions for landowners, specific tax regulations for urban land, credit and loans, as well as incentives for innovative agricultural activities (e.g. indoor farming, high-tech farming, etc.).

The management and development of UPA facilities and infrastructures, is a key aspect for ensuring success of UPA initiatives. This might include not only the accessibility to specific sites or the normal functioning of UPA plots (e.g. irrigation systems, roads, small facilities, plot layout, fencing, etc.), but also farmer market structures, as well as any potential decontamination and soil rehabilitation work.

Public bodies should provide information to citizens about UPA initiatives and promote short chains, local agri-food products, sustainable farming practices, and UPA-related recreation activities. Public bodies should be able to manage any potential social and land use conflicts between UPA practitioners, citizens and the private sector. They may support and facilitate the establishment of agreements with farmers (particularly for public procurement) or associations, as well as with landowners for land allocation. They can offer technical advice and assistance, training and educational activities concerning UPA, for schools, practitioners, urban planners and politicians.

This step includes the evaluation of the effectiveness and outcome of UPA-related policies (projects and plans) through specific monitoring, evaluation and research activities (including the application of a set of indicators) and periodic reports established by the UPA committee.

This Poster presents an abstract of the Task 4.2 "In-depth analysis of urban planning strategies towards UA" (Lead: Politecnico di Torino) of the European Forum on Urban Agriculture H2020 project. It is intended for discussion and consultation with policy makers. The full results, which include "Guidelines to support city authorities in the integration of UA into public policies and planning tools", are illustrated in the Deliverable 4.2. "Report on in-depth-analysis on UAs role in urban planning". Authors: Cassatella C., Gottero E., Cotella G., Salizzoni E., Pede E., Quaglia S., October 2022. See also: Politecnico di Torino, 2022, Planning for and with Urban Agriculture, Poster, available from EFUA website: <https://www.efua.eu/>

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